

Twitter'ıntweet'lerinegöre COVID-19 hakkındakigenelduygularınanalizi

SayınMirzaHammadBaig

CSIT Bölümü, NED MühendislikveTeknolojiÜniversitesi, Pakistan

hello@hammadbaig.com

Sayın Danish Karim

CSIT Bölümü, NED MühendislikveTeknolojiÜniversitesi, Pakistan

danishkarimkhan@gmail.com

Prof. Dr. Noman Islam

IqraÜniversitesi, Pakistan

noman.islam@gmail.com

Analysis of public sentiments about COVID-19 based on twitter's tweets

Mr. MirzaHammadBaig

Department of CSIT, NEDUniversity of Engineering and Technology, Pakistan

hello@hammadbaig.com

Mr. Danish Karim

Department of CSIT, NED University of Engineering and Technology, Pakistan

danishkarimkhan@gmail.com

Prof. Dr. Noman Islam

Iqra University, Pakistan

noman.islam@gmail.com

ÖZET

Her gün öncelikle sosyal medyada büyük miktarda veri üretiliyor. Bu verilerin analizi, kitlelerin farklı durumları hakkında fikirlerini bildirmesine yardımcı olabilir. Bu makale, insanların COVID-19 ile ilgili tweet'lerinin duygusal analizini gerçekleştirir. Duygu analizi, bir kişinin tweet atma anındaki duygusal durumunu belirleme ve herhangi bir yöne eğilim gösterip göstermediğini belirler. COVID-19, toplumun tüm dünyayı çeşitli şekillerde etkiledi. Bazı insanlar işsiz kaldı, birkaç şirket iflas etti ve farklı ülkelerde ciddi ekonomik krizler karşı karşıya kaldı. Milyonlarca insanın hayatını kaybettiği gözlemlendi. Aynı zamanda, daha sonra iyileşen çok sayıda kişiye COVID-19 teşhis kondu. Milyarlarca insan ekonomik ve sosyal etkiden etkilendi. COVID ile ilgili birçok olumlu yön de gözlemlendi. Örneğin, dünyanın birçok şehrinde çevre kirliliği azaltıldı. Diğer nedenlere bağlı ölüm oranları da azalır. Dünyanın çeşitli yerlerinde suç oranlarının da düştüğü görüldü. Bu nedenle, insanların busalın hakkında nedensel ilişkilerini belirlemek önemlidir.

Dünya Sağlık Örgütü (WHO), koronavirüs (COVID-19) küresel bir pandemi olarak ilan ettiğinden bu yana, hükümetler virüs kontrol altına almak için sıkı kilitler koyarken, insanlar bu pandemi ve hükümet kararları hakkındaki görüşlerini ifade etmek için sosyal medyayı (Twitter gibi) kullanıyor. Bu değerli veriler, sağlık profesyonellerinin, hükümetin ve politikacıların insanların duygularına dayalı olarak daha fazla karar almalarına yardımcı olabilir. Bu duygular, pozitif, negatif ve nötr polarite olarak sınıflandırılabilen tweetlerin metni aracılığıyla elde edilebilir. Bu araştırma, COVID-19'a yanıtlar hakkında duygusal analizini sağlar. Analiz için Twitter tweet verileri kullanılır. Analiz, birkaç kitaplık birlikte python kullanılarak yapıldı. Duyguların görselleştirme ve görsel kazanma için grafikler oluşturuldu. Özellikle, kişilerin tweetleri olumlu, olumsuz veya nötr olarak sınıflandırıldı ve bir duyarlılık puanı atandı. Ardından, verilerin görüşlerini elde etmek için kelime bulutları ve diğer görselleştirmeler kullanıldı.

Anahtar Kelimeler—COVID-19, kilitleme, koronavirüs, pandemi, duyarlılık analizi, Twitter.

ABSTRACT

There has been a huge amount of data generated every day primarily on social media. Analyzing this data may allow us to know the masses' opinion about the different states of affairs. This paper performs sentiment analysis of tweets of the people about COVID 19. The sentiment analysis is the process of determining the emotional state of a person at the time of tweeting or giving its opinion by any means. COVID 19 has impacted the society and the whole world in various ways. A number of people have become jobless, several companies have gone bankrupt and different countries have faced severe economic crisis. Loss of lives of millions of people have been observed. At the same time, a large number of people were diagnosed with COVID 19 who later on recovered. Billions of people got affected because of the economic and social impact. A number of positive aspects were also observed related to COVID. For instance, the environmental pollution was reduced in several industrial cities in the world. Death rates due to other causes are also reduced. Crime rates in various parts of the world are also found to be reduced. It is therefore essential to determine what people think about this pandemic.

Since World Health Organization (WHO) declared coronavirus (COVID-19) as a global pandemic, governments have imposed strict lockdowns to contain the virus, whereas people are using social media (such as Twitter) to express their opinions about this pandemic and government's decisions. This precious data can be used for sentiment analysis that can help the health professionals, government and policymakers to make further decisions based on the people's sentiments. These sentiments can be obtained via twitter tweets' text, which can be classified into positive, negative and neutral polarity. This research provides sentiment analysis of the public in response to the COVID-19. Twitter tweets data are used for the analysis. The analysis was done using python along with several libraries. Graphs were generated to visualize the sentiments and gain insights. Specifically, the tweets of the people were classified as positive, negative or neutral, and a sentiment score is assigned. Then, word clouds and other visualizations were used to gain insights of the data.

Keywords— COVID-19, lockdown, coronavirus, pandemic, sentiment analysis, Twitter.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) has declared coronavirus (also known as COVID-19) as a global pandemic on March 11, 2020. The pandemic started originally in China and later affecting the whole world. According to statistics¹, COVID-19 has killed more than a million people so far and disturbed billions of people around the world. Many countries have opted for the strict lockdown to contain the virus that made people worried about their daily lives. People went to social media sites (such as twitter) to express their opinions about COVID-19 outbreak.

Sentiment analysis is the technique used in data analysis to gather people's opinion about a specific situation or event. Every social media has different authenticity, but twitter becomes more reliable these days of the outbreak. The sentiment analysis can give the overall picture of the situation as the people are relying on social media platforms in this unprecedented time.

Several methods and tools have been used for textual analysis, subject to the nature of textual data, size of dataset, research objectives, and context. Tweets have been used widely for textual and sentiments analysis [1].

Existing researches have used different textual classification techniques to assess social media sentiment. One of the paper focused on the Naïve Bayes classification [2]. The paper also explained why VADER is a great choice.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this work, the sentiment analysis was performed on COVID-19 trends via social media (twitter tweets). The objective of the research is to see public's reactions to growing cases. Different research papers have used different techniques for sentiment analysis. For instance, some researchers have focused on pure classification algorithms. A number of researches have used Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) and machine learning for analysis. Most common languages used for sentiment analysis are Python and R. The paragraphs below cite some key contributors about Covid-19 research.

Kaur and Sharma [3] have worked on the analysis of sentiments about coronavirus disease. The Twitter API was used for accumulating tweets on the coronavirus. Afterwards, positive, negative and neutral emotions were analyzed using machine learning techniques tools. For pre-processing of fetched tweets, NLTK library was used and Textblob's dataset was used for analyzing the tweets. The authors have further shown the insight details on positive, negative, neutral sentiments through different visualizations.

P.Kaila [4] applied latent Dirichlet allocation to the Covid-19's data in the form of document term matrix based on the datasets. In a similar direction, Medford [5] produced a list of hashtags related to COVID-19 based on people's opinion. They analyzed the relevant topics over time by using an unsupervised machine learning technique. Alhajji [6] performed sentiment analysis on COVID and discovered more positive tweets than negative based on various measures.

RESEARCH DESIGN & TOOL SELECTION

The initial design for the project is divided into the following steps:

- Data Gathering and Cleaning: GetOldTweets3 library is used for Tweets data extraction. Pre-processing was performed and further cleansing was performed using available Python APIs named RE and LangID.

¹<http://www.worldometers.com>

- Calculating Sentiment Score: Python library named VADER was used to calculate the sentiment score[3].
- Classification of the Tweets: For classification, positive, negative and neutral emotions as per the sentiment score.
- Visualization:The paper used Python APIs (matplotlib.pyplot, seaborn, wordcloud) to generate visualization[4].

Several python libraries were used such as pandas, numpy, sklearn, NLTK (includes VADER), for sentiment analysis. Matplotlib and word cloud was used for visualization and several other common libraries available for machine learning. Classification was performed using python library named VADER. It is based on lexicons of sentiment related words where each word in the lexicon rated whether the word is positive, negative or neutral.

PROPOSED APPROACH

The proposed work can be divided into four major phases as shown in the Fig 1.

Figure 1: Major phases of proposed work

1. Data collection

The data for this project is collected from multiple resources given below.

- Tweets Dataset from kaggle
- IEEE data port kaggle
- GetOldTweets (python Library)
- Several other sources.

2. Pre-processing of the raw data

In this step, the cleaning and preprocessing were done on the raw data to convert into desired format, so that it can be used for analysis. This includes the following major tasks:

- Removing URLs from the tweets
- Conversion of all text into lowercase,
- Removing punctuations
- Removing stopwords

3. Sentiment analysis using the library(s)

To perform sentiment analysis on the data, a list of all words were compiled and then it is used to determine the term Frequency. Finally, the sentiment score for each tweet was determined and then they are provided the score based on polarity value. Final step is plotting of the sentiment score counts.

4. Representation (Visualization) of the output

For representation, we created different types of graphs based on output by using python libraries to analyze different aspects of the data.

IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

This section talks about the implementation details. It comprises:

- Integrating the data and reading tweets data
- Generating time-frequency graph to check the frequency of the tweets, as shown in Fig 2.

Figure 2: Time Frequency graph of tweets

- Converting the tweet into texts,
- Removing the URLs text from tweets so it becomes plain text. Fig 3 shows the tweets after removing URL.

```
0 As a response to COVID19, 30% of companies sur...
1 @NCDCgov Covid-19 Positive results coming from...
2 #keepseniors safe Despite a severe uptick in pr...
3 Wuhan has reached the grim milestone of ...
4 People may blame #China for #COVID19, but many...
Name: text, dtype: object
```

Figure 3: Removing URLs from tweets

- For case sensitive data converted all tweets to the lowercase. Fig 4 shows the results after case normalization.

```

0   as a response to covid19, 30% of companies sur...
1   @ncdcgov covid-19 positive results coming from...
2   #keepseniorssafe despite a severe uptick in pr...
3   Wuhan has reached the grim milestone of ...
4   people may blame #china for #covid19, but many...
Name: text, dtype: object

```

Figure 4: Normalizing the case of tweets

- Removing all the punctuations for easier readability.

```

0   as a response to covid19 30 of companies surve...
1   ncdcgov covid19 positive results coming from k...
2   keepseniorssafe despite a severe uptick in pro...
3   Wuhan has reached the grim milestone of ...
4   people may blame china for covid19 but many ch...
Name: text, dtype: object

```

Figure 5: Removing punctuations from tweets

- Removed all stop words, because with stop words, difficult to read the sentence. Fig 6 shows the result.

```

0   response 30 companies surveyed offering home o...
1   ncdcgov positive results coming kano alarming ...
2   keepseniorssafe despite severe uptick protocol...
3   Wuhan reached grim milestone 10000plus c...
4   people may blame china many chinese citizens a...
Name: text, dtype: object

```

Figure 6: Removing stop words from tweets

- Made a list for all tweets words as shown in Fig 7.

```
['response', '30', 'companies', 'surveyed', 'offering']
```

Figure 7: Tweet words

- To calculate the term frequency, made a graph to get the frequency

Figure 8: Term frequency graph

- For sentiment analysis, generated polarity scores for every tweet, as shown in Fig 9.

	neg	neu	pos	compound
1420765	0.183	0.634	0.183	0.0000
1420766	0.341	0.659	0.000	-0.8316
1420767	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.0000
1420768	0.000	1.000	0.000	0.0000
1420769	0.277	0.630	0.093	-0.8519

Figure 9: Sentiment analysis scores

- Classifying the scores based on the compound polarity value into positive/negative (Fig 10).

	neg	neu	pos	compound	val
0	0.000	0.635	0.365	0.8720	positive
1	0.111	0.563	0.327	0.8431	positive
2	0.000	0.752	0.248	0.6467	positive
3	0.366	0.495	0.139	-0.5106	negative
4	0.270	0.730	0.000	-0.5859	negative

Figure 10: Classifying the tweets into positive and negative

- Plotting the sentiment count scores w.r.t positive/negative/neutral. Fig 11 shows the results. It can be seen that most of the people things positively about the COVID-19 situation.

Figure 11: Sentiments of people

- The temporal plot of the sentiments (To check time series analysis). Fig 12 shows the results

Figure 12: Temporal plot of sentiments

- Calculate the distribution of sentiment scores as shown in Fig 13.

Figure 13: Sentiments' distribution

- The word cloud of polar words in all the tweets are also determined. Fig 14 shows the word cloud from positive and negative tweets. It can be seen that for positive tweets the dominant terms are pandemic, crisis, deaths. For negative tweets, the dominant terms are lock down, health.
- Fig 15 shows the word cloud for neutral and all the tweets. It can be seen that the dominant terms are almost the same. Lockdown, health. Some new terms such as trump, state, read are also used.

Figure 14: Word cloud for positive and negative tweets

Figure 15: Word cloud for neutral and over all tweets

V. CONCLUSION

This research deals with the sentiment analysis of the public in response to the COVID-19. Twitter's tweets data were used for the analysis. The analysis was done using python along with several libraries. Several graphs were generated to visualize the sentiments. Moreover, it is observed that public sentiments toward COVID-19 are positive.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Ahmad, A. Ramsay, and H. Ahmed, "Detecting emotions in English and Arabic tweets," *Inf.*, 2019, doi: 10.3390/info10030098.
- [2] C. J. Hutto and E. Gilbert, "VADER: A parsimonious rule-based model for sentiment analysis of social media text," in proceedings of *International Conference on Weblogs and Social Media*, 2014.
- [3] C. Kaur and A. Sharma, "Twitter sentiment analysis on Coronavirus using Textblob," *EasyChairPrepr.*, 2020.
- [4] R. P. Kaila and A. V. K. Prasad, "Informational flow on twitter-corona virus outbreak-topic modelling approach," *Int. J. Adv. Res. Eng. Technol.*, 2020, doi: 10.34218/IJARET.11.3.2020.011.
- [5] R. J. Medford, S. N. Saleh, A. Sumarsono, T. M. Perl, and C. U. Lehmann, "An 'Infodemic': Leveraging high-volume Twitter data to understand the public sentiment for the COVID-19 outbreak," *medRxiv*. 2020, doi: 10.1101/2020.04.03.20052936.
- [6] M. Alhajji, Mohammed, Abdullah, Mohammed, "Sentiment analysis of tweets in Saudi Arabia regarding governmental preventive measures to contain COVID-19," *Preprints*, 2020.
- [7] McKinsey & Company, "COVID-19: Briefing Materials," *McKinsey Co.*, 2020.
- [8] Abdul-Al Razzaq, D. Alhuwail, Househ M., Hamdi M. "Top concerns of tweeters during the COVID-19 pandemic situation Infoveillance study" *J. Med. Internet Res.*, 22 (4) (2020)
- [9] A. D. Dubey, "Twitter Sentiment Analysis during COVID-19 Outbreak," Jaipuria Institute of Management, Jaipur, March, vol., pp. 1-9, 2020.
- [10] N. Rajput, B. A. Grover, and V. K. Rathi, "Word frequency and sentiment analysis of twitter tweets during Coronavirus pandemic," arxiv.org, April, 2020.
- [11] R. Muthusami & A. Bharathi & K. Saritha. "COVID-19 Outbreak: Tweet based Analysis and Visualization towards the Influence of Coronavirus in the World.", 2020 *Gedrag & Organisatie Review*. 33. 10.37896/GOR33.02/062.
- [12] P. Tyagi and R. J. A. S. Tripathi, "A Review towards the Sentiment Analysis Techniques for the Analysis of Twitter Data tweets," in proceedings of *2nd International Conference on Advanced Computing and Software Engineering (ICACSE)* 2019.
- [13] C. Kaur and A. Sharma, "Twitter Sentiment Analysis on Coronavirus using Textblobs," *EasyChair* 2716-2314, 2020.
- [14] O. Gencoglu and M. Gruber, "Causal Modeling of Twitter Activity During COVID-19 situation," pp. 1-13, 2020.
- [15] Sailunaz, Kashfia & Alhajj, Reda. (2019). Emotion and Sentiment Analysis from Twitter Text. *Journal of Computational Science*. 36. 10.1016/j.jocs.2019.05.009.
- [16] O. Gencoglu and M. Gruber, "Causal Modeling of Twitter Activity During COVID-19 pandemic," *Computation*, pp. 1-10, 2020.